

ABSTRACT

This descriptive–survey study was conducted to assess the level of knowledge on disaster risk reduction and management during natural disasters of 190 barangay officials in Barbaza, Antique. The respondents were grouped as to age, sex, educational attainment, and length of service as barangay officials. The data gathered were subjected to descriptive statistical tests and inferential analysis using a t-test, and the Analysis of Variance was set at a 0.05 level of significance. Results showed that barangay officials were moderately knowledgeable about disaster risk reduction and management. It shows no significant difference in the knowledge on disaster risk reduction and management for natural disasters when classified according to sex and educational attainment and significant when classified according to age and length of service. Further, it is recommended for the barangay council conduct an information campaign on DRRM, training, and drills related to its programs and guidelines by collaborating with government and non-government agencies.

Keywords: *Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, Descriptive-survey, Barbaza, Antique*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change has brought tremendous ranges of effects to many countries' ecosystems bringing about extreme weather conditions. Inevitable natural disasters have long been occurring in the country, but these have become more frequent, stronger, and more hazardous in recent years.

In 2013, the deadliest typhoon that caused catastrophic destruction entered the Philippine area of responsibility, specifically in Western Visayas; it was named internationally as Haiyan but locally named Yolanda. The destruction was on a massive scale. Thousands of lives were lost, infrastructures were devastated, the means of livelihood of many people were damaged, and the region's economy was greatly affected.

Western Visayas region and the Province of Antique are similar in terms of location and being at risk for disastrous natural calamities like typhoons and earthquakes. Nine major tropical storms struck the province in the past three years, affecting fifty-one thousand families or two hundred thirty thousand (230,000) individuals. Historically, a tsunami caused the loss of lives of many in Barbaza, Antique, hundreds of years ago (Antique Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office, 2016). The natural calamities that frequently affected the country were observed to be disastrous, and their effects led to the suffering of its people. The effects of disaster keep challenging government officials from the lowest local level of the government (the barangay) up to the highest national level. The hardships caused by the hostile environment have to be counteracted, as government officials observed, thus the conceptualization of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Program. It is believed that with this program, the hazardous effects of natural disasters will be prevented or minimized.

Though disasters have been occurring already in the province, an assessment has yet to be conducted on knowledge and attitude on disaster risk reduction and management among local government officials, specifically barangay officials in the municipality of Barbaza; thus, this study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The investigation utilized descriptive research employing the survey-analysis method. The researcher made an instrument entitled the knowledge on Disaster Reduction and management questionnaire used in the study. Upon retrieval of the accomplished questionnaires, the data were tallied, computed, analyzed, and interpreted using statistical software or programs and subject to specific statistical treatments.

Participants/Respondents. The purposive sampling technique was used because the study included 190 barangay officials who served as the study's respondents. The total population of the said barangay officials was utilized in this study.

Data Collection Procedure. The researchers wrote a letter seeking permission from the barangay captain of Barbaza, Antique, to allow the conduct of the study in their esteemed local government unit. After securing the necessary permits, the researchers crafted a researcher-made instrument to be utilized in the conduct of the survey. Once validated and tested for reliability, the researchers scheduled the actual conduct of data gathering to extract appropriate data for utilization in this study.

Data Analysis Procedure. For the data analysis of this study, the researchers utilized frequency count, weighted mean, and t-test. To gather the demographic profile of the respondents, frequency count was used. A weighted mean was utilized to measure the knowledge of disaster risk reduction and management of the barangay officials of Barbaza, Antique. Finally, to materialize the measurement of the difference in the level of knowledge on disaster risk reduction and management, t-test was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the respondents' demographic profiles grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment, and length of service.

Table 1 . Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	f	%
Entire group	195	100
age		
Young	44	23
Old	151	77
Sex		
Male	115	59
Female	80	41
Educational Attainment		
Elementary	46	24
High School	81	41
College	68	35
Length of Service		
Short(below 5 years)	114	58
Long (5 years and above)	81	42

As an entire group, the knowledge of disaster risk reduction and management for natural disasters was moderately knowledgeable, with a mean of 4.1292 and an S.D. of .44928. In general, the knowledge on disaster risk reduction and management for natural disasters was moderately knowledgeable, with the means that fall between the interval of 3.41 to 4.20.

When age was considered, the level of knowledge on disaster risk reduction and management for natural disasters for those below 35 years old and 35 years old and above was moderately knowledgeable, with a mean of 4.0045 and 4.1652, respectively.

Regarding sex, the level of knowledge on disaster risk reduction and management for natural disasters for males and females was moderately knowledgeable, with a mean of 4.1113 and 4.1549, respectively.

When educational attainment was considered, elementary, high school, and college had a mean of 4.0520, 4.1228, and 4.1897, respectively, which was moderately knowledgeable.

When the length of service was considered, below five years had a mean of 4.0088, which was moderately knowledgeable, while five years and above, with a mean of 4.2981, was very knowledgeable.

Table 2. Level of knowledge on disaster risk reduction and management for natural disasters classified according to certain variables

Category	Mean	SD	Description
Entire Group	4.1290	.44928	Moderately Knowledgeable
Age			
Young	4.0045	.60095	Moderately Knowledgeable
Old	4.1652	.38944	Moderately Knowledgeable
Sex			
Male	4.1113	.48828	Moderately Knowledgeable
Female	4.1544	.39867	Moderately Knowledgeable
Educational Attainment			
Elementary	4.0520	.39073	Moderately Knowledgeable
High School	4.1228	.48193	Moderately Knowledgeable
College	4.1897	.44332	Moderately Knowledgeable
Length of service			
Below five years	4.0088	.47770	Moderately Knowledgeable
Five years and above	4.2981	.34291	Very Knowledgeable
Legend:	4.21- 5.00	Very Knowledgeable	
	3.41- 4.20	Moderately Knowledgeable	
	2.61- 3.40	Knowledgeable	
	1.81- 2.60	Slightly Knowledgeable	
	1.00- 1.80	Not Knowledgeable	

When age was considered, there was a significant difference between below 35 years old and 35 years old and above, $t=4.436$, $p(0.036)<0.05$. Therefore null hypothesis is rejected.

When sex is considered, there is no significant difference between male and female, $t=0.432$, $p(0.0512)>0.05$. Therefore null hypothesis is accepted.

When the length of service is considered, there was a significant difference between long and short $t=21.746$, $p(0.000)<0.05$. Therefore null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 3. The difference in Level of Effectiveness as to certain variables.

Variable	Mean	t-value	t-prob	Interpretation
Age				
Young	4.0045			
Old	4.1652	4.436	.036	Significant
Sex				
Male	4.1113			Not
Female	4.1544	0.432	.0512	Significant
Length of Service				
Short	4.0088			
Long	4.2981	21.746	.000	Significant

When educational attainment is considered, there was no significant difference between elementary, high school, and college $f=1.344$, $p(0.263)>0.05$. Therefore null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 4. The difference in Level of Effectiveness as to certain variables.

Variable	Mean	f-value	f-prob	Interpretation
Educational Attainment				
Elementary	4.0520			
High School	4.1228			Not
College	4.1897	1.344	.263	Significant

CONCLUSION

The respondents were primarily old, male, in high school, and below five years in service.

In general, the knowledge of disaster risk reduction and management for natural disasters was moderately knowledgeable. Regardless of age, sex, educational attainment, and length of service, the length of service was five years and was very knowledgeable.

Further, it was found that there was no significant difference in the level of knowledge on disaster risk reduction and management for natural disasters when respondents were classified according to sex and educational attainment. While a significant difference when respondents were classified according to age and length of service.

REFERENCES

- Boyle, R. (2000). Performance Measurement in Local Government. CPMR Discussion Paper 15.
- Calde, Nimreh L (2013). Module 2: The Legal Framework of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Policy.
- Cristobal, A. & Cristobal, M.C. (2009). *Guidebook in Research Writing Preparing the Nursing Thesis Proposal*. Quezon City: C&E Publishing.
- Community-Based Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, Basic Instructors' Guide (BIG). OCD-JICA Project Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Capacity Enhancement.
- Gabriel, A.G. and Manuzon, E.D.P. (2016) Management, Decision Making Styles and Training Preferences of Barangay Officials in Nueva Ecija Philippines. *North Asian International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2, 93-110.
- Ganpatrao, JS. (2014). Knowledge and Practices of School Teachers Regarding Disaster Management. *International Journal of Health System and Disaster Management*.
- National Risk Reduction and Management Plan 2011-2028. *From* <http://www.ndrrmc.gov.ph/index.php/13-disaster-risk-reduction-and-management-laws/41-national-disaster-risk-reduction-and-management-plan-2011-2028>
- National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Plan (NDRRMP), 2011-2028.
- National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Framework (NDRRMF), 2011.
- PD 1566: Strengthening the Philippine Disaster Control Capability and Establishing the National Program on Community Disaster Preparedness. *From* <http://www.lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra2010/ra-10121-2010.html>
- Republic Act 10121, Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010.
- Republic Act 7160, "The local government code of the Philippines," 1991.
- Risk Reduction in Practice: A Philippine Case Study. *Retrieved from* <http://www.ifrc.org/Global/Case%20studies/Disasters/cs-philippines.pdf>

Robas, R.J.O. (2010). Flood Disaster Risk Reduction and Risk Management of Pasig City. *From* https://www.academia.edu/7294706/Flood_Disater_Risk_Reduction_and_Risk_Managemen_t_of_Pasig_City

UNISDR (2016) What Is Disaster Risk Reduction? The United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction. [https://www.unisdr.org/who-we-are/what-is-drr\](https://www.unisdr.org/who-we-are/what-is-drr/)

Yang, C., Liu, H. and Wang, X. (2013). Organization Theories: From Classical to modern. *Journal of Applied Science*, 13, 4470-4476. <https://doi.org/10.3923/jas.2013.4470.4476>

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